

COMPARATIVE APPLICATION OF MASS MEDIA TERMS

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Abstract: In the modern conditions of the formation of the information society, the study of the language of mass media is of particular importance, and until recently, the activity of language in the field of mass media was studied by various branches of linguistics - sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics, cognitive linguistics, etc. All conditions for existing were considered and compared.

Keywords: mediallynguistics, mass media, media texts, ICT, print media, comparative analysis.

Аннотация: В современных условиях формирования информационного общества изучение языка средств массовой информации приобретает особое значение, и до недавнего времени деятельность языка в сфере средств массовой информации изучалась различными разделами лингвистики - социолингвистикой, психолингвистикой, когнитивной лингвистикой и др. Были рассмотрены и сопоставлены все условия для существования.

Ключевые слова: медиалингвистика, средства массовой информации, медиатексты, ИКТ, печатные СМИ, сравнительный анализ.

Introduction

The literature of each period is distinguished by the superiority of its form. The second half of the 20th century is a new field of speech use, the rapid growth of mass communication. Rapid development of traditional media:

- printed publications;
- radio;
- television;
- the emergence of new computer information technologies.

Globalization of the world information space - all this did not affect the production process and the spread of the word. Media texts or media texts are one of the most common forms of language availability today.[1]

Media texts in English occupy a special place in the global information flow. Due to a number of political, economic and socio-cultural reasons, the total volume of media texts in English significantly exceeds the volume of media texts in other languages.

Literature Analysis And Methodology

The term "mediallynguistics" was formed by analogy with a number of similar lexical units used to name new academic disciplines that appear at the intersection of sciences - sociolinguistics, ethnoinguistics, media psychology, media economics, etc. The term "mediallynguistics" appeared in Russian scientific usage relatively recently, in 2000. It was used for the first time in TDGDobrosklonskaya's doctoral thesis "Theory and Methods of

Media Linguistics" [2], A little earlier its English version "media linguistics" appeared, which can be found in the works of British researchers.

The subject of this new science is the study of the activity of language in the field of mass communication. That is, mediallynguistics deals with a comprehensive study of a certain area of speech use - the language of mass media. The legitimacy of emphasizing media linguistics as a new direction of linguistics is related to the enormous role that mass media play for society and the individual. Most of the modern speech practices are used in the field of mass communication. The continuous improvement of information and communication technologies (ICT) leads to a steady increase in the total volume of texts distributed in different national languages in the global information space. At the same time, the subject of media linguistics is not the only discipline that has become a specific field of speech use: the same principle is used to separate another new field of linguistic research - political linguistics into an independent discipline. its study is the activity of the language in the field of political relations.[3]

Results

The study of various aspects of the use of speech in the rapidly developing field of mass communication not only led to the formation of the concept of "media language", but also served the formation of a new direction in modern linguistics - mediallynguistics. MediaThe subject of linguistics comprehensively studies the functioning of language in the field of mass communication or "the word in mass media". Within media linguistics, all previously disparate studies of various aspects of media discourse have been combined into a single systematic framework.[4]

The internal structure of media linguistics reflects a holistic view of the subject. All components and levels of mass media texts are deeply analyzed in a combination of linguistic and extralinguistic factors: the influence of the methods of creation and distribution of media texts on their linguistic and format features, functional-genre classification, phonological, syntagmatic issues and stylistic features, interpretation features, cultural features, ideological modality, pragmalinguistic value.

The main theoretical basis of media linguistics is the concept of media text, in which media text is considered as a dialectical unity of linguistic and media features representing a multi-layered, multi-level phenomenon. The main levels of media discourse include the spoken text level, the video sequence or graphic image level, and the audio accompaniment level. Diversity is understood.

Discussion

For media linguistics, the author is important as a unique person, his views, social position. Taking into account the experience of researchers, we prefer to work with the concept of "authorship" within the framework of the school of mediallynguistics.

Carrying out a comparative analysis, it should be said that the ways of expressing modality in English, regardless of the stylistic features of the text, are characterized by a special accuracy related to the semantic potential of the system of modal verbs. English modal verbs are a group of verbs that refer to an action rather than to the action itself. Therefore, Russian equivalents of English modal verbs are often found in the group of can, need, required, type predicates, as well as Uzbek adverbs of English modal predicates and adverbial phrases with semantic similarity exist, probably, probably, must, must, etc.

That surplus has to be invested somewhere, and while Manchester City might be attractive,

there aren't enough football clubs to go around. "This surplus should be invested somewhere, and although Manchester City is attractive, there are not enough football clubs for everyone.[6]

At the same time, it should be noted that the use of English modal verbs from these Uzbek equivalents corresponds to the technique of not naming the subject. But it is quite possible to translate English modal structures into Uzbek equivalent modal verbs and indicative mood verbs. Thus, in general, despite the typological differences between the Uzbek and English languages, the common conceptual meaning has been preserved.[5,6]

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that medialogistics is a science that studies the activity of language in the media sphere, which appeared relatively recently. It was created at the intersection of two disciplines, therefore, it embodies its own characteristics: on the one hand, it uses the base of linguistic research, and on the other hand, it is included in the general system of medialogy. media studies. Its main category is the media text, which is a complex and complex phenomenon that combines a number of characteristic features

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